

Informed Consent · AESTIMATIO Pilot Study 2026 Q3

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Study Information

Study title: AESTIMATIO Pilot Study 2026 Q3 — Empirical Calibration of a Multidimensional Valuation Model for Personhood and Labor Time

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Date: _____

1 What this is about

The AESTIMATIO research develops a model for the multidimensional valuation of personhood and labor time. The model considers, alongside market price, eight further impact dimensions (reproduction, accumulated capital, social impact, knowledge contribution, ecology, self-effect, third-party effect, scarcity).

This pilot study examines whether the elicitation instruments are reliable and whether the model constants are plausibly calibrated. It is preparation for a larger main study.

2 What happens to you

If you participate, you will:

- in **week 1** (ca. 45 minutes) fill out a self-disclosure sheet on your activity, your cost of living, your accumulation of knowledge and experience, your ecological footprint, your self-effect (well-being in work), your market price, and your professional scarcity;
- nominate three peer assessors from your work environment (colleagues, principals, clients/customers) who will fill out a short sheet on your social impact and third-party effect;
- in **week 5** (ca. 15 minutes) repeat the self-effect part to test the stability of the elicitation (test-retest);
- in **week 6** (ca. 45 minutes) conduct a semi-structured follow-up interview with the author about your experiences with the elicitation, the comprehensibility of the axes, and your application ideas.

Total effort: ca. 2.5 hours over 6 weeks.

3 What I do with your data

- Your data will be **pseudonymized** (you will receive a pseudonym such as P-2026-Q3-001).
- Identifying information (real name, email) will be stored **separately** from the substantive data.
- Storage takes place **locally encrypted** on the author's hard drive. No cloud storage.
- **Only the author** has access to the raw data. No transmission to third parties.
- I publish **only aggregated and anonymized results**. No individual cases.
- Anonymized data may be published as an open-data dataset (CSV with codebook), if you consent.

4 Your Rights

You have the right:

- to **participate voluntarily** and to withdraw at any time without justification;
- to receive **information** about the data stored about you;
- to request **correction** or **deletion** of your data;
- to request **data portability** (you receive a copy of your data);
- to file a **complaint** with the data protection authority.

Upon withdrawal, your data will be irrevocably deleted within 14 days (insofar as aggregated results have not yet been published).

5 Protective Rule for Exhaustion Indicators

The elicitation part on self-effect (W6) is an adaptation of the Maslach Burnout Inventory. It may indicate exhaustion states. If your answers to certain items exceed a particular threshold:

- you will receive a **confidential notification** clarifying that this is only a hint and not a clinical judgment;
- you will receive a **list of advisory services** (Telefonseelsorge, mental health contact points in AT/DE/CH);
- the **study analysis continues unchanged**, if you wish;
- in case of acute crisis signals (e.g., suicidal thoughts) the **study participation will be paused** and referral to professional advisory services will be offered.

6 Conflict of Interest Disclosure

The author is simultaneously model developer and study conductor. There is **no financial interest** in a specific study outcome: the application will be published under free licenses (AGPL-3.0 for code, CC BY 4.0 for texts); commercialization by the author is not planned. Negative results (e.g., insufficient reliability) will also be published.

7 For Questions or Complaints

Contact: Thomas Schüller · forschung@tschueller.com

Consent Declaration

Pseudonym: _____ (assigned by the author)

Date: _____

I, _____ (real name),

confirm with my signature below that:

- I have read and understood the study information;
- I have had the opportunity to ask questions, and all questions have been answered comprehensibly;
- I understand that participation is voluntary and I can withdraw at any time without justification;
- I understand that my data will be pseudonymized and treated confidentially;
- I **consent** to the elicitation according to the methodology described above.

Additionally (optional):

- I consent that my anonymized data may be published as an open-data dataset.
- I would like to be informed about the results of the study by email.
- In case of an indication notification regarding W6, I agree to its dispatch to the email address below.

Email address for inquiries and possibly indication notification:

Signature:

Place, date:

Note: This consent declaration is issued in two copies. One copy remains with the author, one copy with the participating person.

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This is the EN twin version of `consent_aestimatio_pilot.md` (DE primary). In case of divergence between DE and EN, the DE version is the tie-breaker per parity rule #27.